

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

INTERPRETATION OF THE CHARACTERISTICS OF THE ELEMENTS OF THE "ASSESSMENT OF STUDENT ACHIEVEMENTS" BLOCK OF SUBJECT CURRICULA BASED ON THE "SYSTEM-STRUCTURE" APPROACH

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Abstract

In the article, it is emphasized that the curriculum reform is conditioned by the need to ensure the adequacy of the implementation of education in Azerbaijan to the challenges of the 21st century, to train a creative, self-developing personality. Also, in the research work, the importance of the educator's reference to the "system-structure" approach both in familiarizing himself with the essence of the "General education program" and in his practical activities related to its implementation is drawn into the center of attention.

The article presents adequate generalizations of the evidence collected on the basis of the "system-structure" dialectical approach, which aims to reveal the nature of the sub-systems included in the "Assessment of Student Achievements" block of the "block-scheme" form of the structure of subject curricula in general education schools of Azerbaijan.

Keywords: educational program. Curriculum, diagnostic, formative, summative assessment, in-school assessment, assessment tools, assessment standards.

Relevance of the research topic

Observations show that mistakes are made in the activities of educators in the application of the subject curriculum at the general education level. This has a negative effect on the efficiency level of the teaching process of the relevant subject.

It is undeniable that the level of understanding of any real existence (objective existence) has a determining effect on the results of using it in adequate directions. On the basis of our scientific observations over the past ten years (at the stage of applying a new approach to the philosophy of general education in Azerbaijan), we have come to the conclusion that, in addition to a number of reasons, the essence of the subject curriculum is not sufficiently understood by these subjects at the basis of the errors manifested in the activities of educators in the process of using subject curricula. honest lack of understanding stops.

Based on our current experience in the field of scientific activity, we claim that the "system-structure" approach (the idea of L. Bertalanf [14;8], which is the basis of system analysis) is the most reliable dialectical method of understanding any objective reality (material or spiritual) and getting to its essence. , in other words, it is a way of spiritual awakening (It is essentially a form of cognitive action). The analysis of the materials

we have collected gives reason to say that this method is not used enough in the theoretical and technological directions regarding the discovery of the essence of the subject curriculum and the determination of its application methods. Therefore, we recommend that only one of the many issues aimed at solving the problem that created the basis for the manifestation of the above-mentioned error - "The interpretation of the characteristics of the elements of the "Assessment of student achievements" block of the subject curricula applied in the general education schools of Azerbaijan" and its actual We claim to be a research topic.

Interpretation of generalizations formed on the basis of research materials

It is known that "in the 21st century, the main value in the life and development of both society and each of its members is a creative, self-developing personality" [15; 16] and there is also the fact that education cannot exist outside the realities of a changing world. [11] Therefore, since the main value in the modern period is a creative, self-developing personality, the educational process should form creativity and self-development abilities in the child. This, in turn, is based on activity, the need to understand and abilities, which are interpreted by the schematic representation below: (Scheme 1):

Scheme 1.

Despite what has been said, a student who has completed general education should be able to: analyze the texts of different styles and genres that he listens to and reads, convey their content to someone else in a concise and partly extensive form; to use monologue and dialogue forms of speech; preparing a plan, thesis, overview, project, opinion; to logically justify their ideas through examples and evidence, to summarize the main points expressed in different ideas; perform calculations and programming, use mathematical language, build algorithms, make assumptions; to use the methods and means of observation, measurement, calculation, experiment, evaluation to understand the surrounding world; to explain the nature of the basic regularities in nature and their interrelation; to compare, classify and present various facts, opinions and evidence; independently perform tasks that require creativity in the training process; to use different sources of information to perform training tasks; to consciously determine one's capabilities, inclination and interest, to demonstrate voluntary and involuntary qualities; to evaluate the results of his work; to follow public behavior, as well as relevant safety and medical-hygiene rules, healthy lifestyle norms; to demonstrate

that he has national, moral, legal, aesthetic values, citizenship position, and leadership qualities; to work together in solving problems, to evaluate the performance of oneself and others in the collective work process; to communicate in a foreign language and so on.

The listed skills of the student who has completed his general education - the general learning results are formed as a synthesis and dialectical unification of the results targeted in the teaching process of all subjects taught in general education schools.

"Revealing the child's creative abilities and realizing them, creating favorable conditions for the formation of his personality is one of the main goals of education." [7; 290-292] There is no doubt that subjects, which are the main enabling components of the implementation of general education, are of high value as an important tool in the formation of the personality of schoolchildren. The "enabling" functions of subjects have found their expression in the Education Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan. [2; 21-23] The mentioned functions can be presented in the form of a scheme as follows: (Scheme 2)

Scheme 2

Based on official state documents, we can state the opinion that "the content of general education subjects aims at the following hierarchical goals by dividing them into different levels of education":

- to inculcate reading, writing and calculation skills in students at the primary education level, to form in them basic knowledge about man, society and nature, elements of logical thinking, aesthetic and artistic taste and other characteristics;

- to evaluate oral speech and writing culture, communication skills, cognitive activity, development of logical thinking, the formation of relevant knowledge and ideas about the subjects included in the educational program as well as the development of world civilization, the ability to use modern information and communication tools, events and provide the ability to determine their future directions of action;

- realization of talents and abilities, preparation for independent life and professional choice, formation of an active citizen position, respect for national and universal values, human rights and freedoms and tolerance, free use of modern information and communication technologies and other technical means, economic acquiring the basics of knowledge, communicating in one or more foreign languages, etc. ensure. (for more details see: [2])

In the mentioned system of knowledge, skills and habits, what is obtained at different educational levels in the teaching of any subject is included as a component. The mentioned components are expressed in the relevant official document. [1]

According to our understanding, it is of particular importance that the subject teacher honestly knows the tasks set before the general education (the expected general results). This is necessary to put the activity related to the educational process into a result-oriented system.

As is known, the goal is a system-creative component in all processes, as well as training-activity.

At the same time, in order to achieve the goal (otherwise, the result will not be achieved), it is very important to implement the training process in what content, based on which strategy, and based on which evaluation mechanisms. [12;71]

As is known, the teacher should be able to find both theoretical and practical answers to all questions related to the learning process. He should know which model he uses in the process of which he is a facilitator and what specific features this model has.

Based on what we have said, it can be concluded that the curriculum of any subject is a set of documents that reflect all the activities aimed at achieving the general learning results and are directed to the capabilities and needs of each student by determining the main goals of the training of that subject in general education schools. The subject curriculum is designed on the basis of result-oriented content standards and involves regular assessment of progress in student achievement to ensure the mastery of the standards, and while setting content standards, the main goal is to gradually increase the speed of progress in student achievement, and it prioritizes instilling the necessary skills needed in daily life to students. [1]

The teacher is one of the subjects of the "enabling function" in the implementation of the educational program. The level of his penetration into the essence of the mentioned program has a conditioning effect on the effectiveness of its activity. Therefore, it is important to refer to the "system-structure" approach both in familiarization with the essence of the program and in the practical activities related to its implementation, which the analysis of research materials and our work experience brings us to this conclusion. The educational program (curriculum) determines the content of education and the rules of mastering it at different levels and levels of education in accordance with the state educational standards. [9; 106-107] The educational program includes the curriculum, educational programs for subjects,

recommendations on methodical provision, assessment and other relevant educational technologies. [8;173] Listed are subsystems of the Education program - complete.

The main goal in determining content standards for subjects is to set goals for the mastery of those standards by each student. In order to achieve knowledge and skills according to the accepted standards, the activity of each student should be continuously stimulated, and the necessary conditions should be created for them to master higher-level standards. Ideally, no learner should be allowed to fall behind throughout the school year, but instead, the focus should be on each learner's progress. Despite what has been said, it can be argued that the application of evaluation mechanisms in the process of education implementation is a necessity, in other words, the evaluation of the student's achievements is a continuous, dynamic (in many cases informal) process. In this process, it is important for the teachers to observe the students and for the purpose of mastering the necessary part of human experience, those who direct their activities (those who want to learn - students in secondary schools) perform class work and homework, and focus on their written and oral answers. It should be emphasized here that evaluation is one of the main psychological problems of group life (corporate-based activity). It is a well-known fact that the emotional or intellectual, moral or aesthetic values that people give to each other play an important role not only in the formation of personality in the process of activity and communication, but also in interpersonal

relations. Pedagogical assessment appears as a special type of assessment. It has been proven many years ago that the price is of great importance as an educational tool. It has been determined that the grade has a profound effect not only on the student's intellectual work, but also on the affective-will field through the feelings of success and failure experienced by him, on the formation of the level of claims, intentions and attitudes. In school experience, grades have historically emerged as a means of creating motivation.

The issue of objectivity of pedagogical assessment has always been relevant. No matter how much importance is given to grade criteria in pedagogy and subject teaching methods, subjective factors play an important role in the evaluation process. It should not be forgotten that the effects of pedagogical assessment are an important psychological-pedagogical problem, related to the formation of the demand-motivation field (forming the student's demand-motivation field, creating favorable conditions for his self-actualization is a prerequisite for the effectiveness of teaching activities.).

The results of a properly conducted assessment allow making decisions about the teacher's activity, how well this activity meets the needs of students, as well as the need to make appropriate changes in the curriculum, planning and textbooks. Assessment of student achievement is considered as the process of collecting information about the student's ability to acquire knowledge, use it, and draw conclusions, and serves the following purposes: (see Scheme 3)

Scheme 3

Assessment and learning processes are seen as two interrelated aspects of education. Evaluation, which is a systematic process, is an effective means of feedback between learning outcomes and stakeholders. (see Scheme 4)

Scheme 4

It is stipulated that a new evaluation system related to the application of the curriculum model in Azerbaijan's general education schools will be brought to the agenda. (see Scheme 5)

Scheme 5.

The modern evaluation policy can be described in the form of a block diagram as follows: (Scheme 6.)

Scheme 6

A number of principles should be kept in focus in the implementation of the evaluation process. These include: (Scheme 7)

Scheme 7

There are directions of assessment with different form, content and purpose. Assessment in Azerbaijan is carried out in three directions: (Scheme 8)

Scheme 8

In particular, let us emphasize that national and international evaluation are evaluation studies conducted to determine perspectives in education and are carried out by special institutions. In-school assessment is a formal assessment and serves to move students from grade to grade, from one educational level to another. International assessment: a) is based on international standards; b) is the result of integration processes in society; c) provides opportunities for citizens of each country to study in other countries; d) held by international and national experts. National assessment: a) is conducted by national institutions; b)

is conducted in order to determine the level of training results at all levels and levels. Types of in-school assessment include diagnostic assessment (initial level assessment), formative assessment (development monitoring), summative (final) assessment. [9; 338-340]

As a side note, let's note that in order to clarify the nature of the modern assessment, it is useful to compare it with the traditional assessment, and we consider it acceptable to conduct the said comparison according to the following parameters: (see Scheme 9)

Scheme 9.

In order to increase the efficiency of the comparison, the interpretation of the traditional and modern assessment by components can be given in the form of a table as follows: (see: Table 1)

Table 1

Components	Traditional assessment	Modern assessment
Objectives	It was considered focused on the development of knowledge, skills, and habits; In reality, the level of knowledge was mainly assessed.	It is focused on the development of knowledge, skills, habits, values, personality; the student's achievement (gained values) is evaluated, his development is systematically monitored.
Roles and responsibilities	Assessment was seen as giving a grade to the student; the student studied only to get a grade; it was applied only in a certain part of the educational process.	Assessment is aimed at improving the quality of education and appears as an important factor that controls it, it is applied at all stages of the educational process.
Types and directions	In-school current and final assessment	International, national, intra-school assessment; Diagnostic, formative, summative assessment
Features	It was more formal, imprecise, based on the teacher's subjective opinion, and unsystematic.	It is based on the standard. It is more objective, accurate, adequate, systematic.
Criteria, indicators	It is a subject-based achievement assessment. More quantitative indicators are taken into account.	Based on assessment standards. Quality indicators are taken into account.
Methods and tools	Limited and inflexible (oral response, tests, tests)	More diverse and flexible (interview, conversation, observation, rubrics, tasks, cooperation with parents and other subject teachers, oral responses of students, analysis of students' writing, results of test tasks).
Forms	Intra-class, intra-school	Intra-classroom, intra-school, centralized.

Let's especially emphasize that the diagnostic evaluation serves to determine the initial level of the student's knowledge and skills, directly to the selection of the teacher's training strategies. In general, diagnostic assessment: 1) enables flexible changes in training goals and strategies according to circumstances; 2) allows to get information about students' interests, outlook, environment; 3) creates conditions for individual approach and differential training. In this process, the following goals are aimed: 1) obtaining information about the initial level of knowledge and skills of each student; 2) take into account the individual development characteristics of students and provide an individual approach in planning the training process; 3) determine the training strategy. The time of the diagnostic assessment is determined as follows: 1) at the beginning of the school year, teaching units; 2) as appropriate - at the beginning of sections and chapters; 3) when a necessary situation arises (when a student comes from another school, changes his class, etc.). The results of the diagnostic assessment are not recorded in official documents, the written notes are reflected in the teacher's notebook, and are kept in the class and student portfolio. According to the purpose of diagnostic evaluation, it is carried out in two forms: continuous and short-term. The results of the diagnostic assessment are not recorded in official documents, the written notes are reflected in the teacher's notebook, and are kept in the class and student portfolio. According to the purpose of diagnostic evaluation, it is carried out in two forms: continuous and short-term. Continuous diagnostic assessment: 1. It is carried out at the beginning of the educational level and school year, in a certain part of several lessons; 2. Aims to study the current state of knowledge and skills of the students in the class; 3. During the assessment, the teacher uses the observation method and the tool that implements this method - the observation table, because he studies the areas of development (cognitive, social-emotional, physical-motor) that include the student's knowledge and skills; 4. In this process, the method of cooperation with parents and other subject teachers and survey tools are used to collect more detailed information about the student; 5. It is conducted at the beginning of teaching units, in a certain part of a lesson; 6. The purpose of this process is to collect information about the necessary knowledge and skills of the student in the subject; 7. At this time, the teacher uses assessment methods such as assignment, interview, project, and study, oral question-and-answer, and presentation tools to check the student's knowledge and skills on any subject and section. [5; 294-299]

The formative assessment, which determines the main essence of the in-school assessment, is the constant monitoring of the student's learning activity and the assessment of the level of knowledge and skill acquisition resulting from the content standards determined for any stage of the learning process. Formative evaluation is carried out in order to monitor the progress and setbacks of the student towards the realization of the accepted standards, to eliminate the problems encountered at this time and to guide the student. In this process, the students get acquainted with the assessment criteria in advance. Formative assessment ensures systematic monitoring of the development of each student in the classroom. Through this evaluation, the teacher adjusts the teaching process, learns the needs of students who are not successful and provides them with additional help. Formative assessment is conducted in order to help students achieve learning outcomes and succeed in summative assessment as a result. In scientific sources, the goals set in this process are formulated as follows: the learner: 1) to achieve his learning results by forming his knowledge and skills; 2) study training needs; 3) to ensure the monitoring of progress in the field of training; 4) to investigate the reasons for failure and ensure its development; 5) monitor the acquisition of basic knowledge and skills expected in the content standards for each subject; 6) to develop the ability of self-evaluation and, finally, 7) to ensure the correct orientation and efficiency of the educational process.

According to our opinion, in order to carry out formative assessment and register the results, the teacher should develop the following skills: determine which standard (according to the subject) will be implemented in the subject; determining evaluation criteria based on content standards; develop rubrics for 4 achievement levels (eg level 1, level 2, level 3, level 4) for each assessment criterion.

Summative assessment consists of minor, major and final summative assessment. Small and large summative assessment is carried out in order to measure the student's achievement level with the tools developed on the basis of assessment standards in accordance with the relevant content standards by concluding a certain stage in the learning process. Summative assessment is an assessment of students' achievements according to standards at any stage of education (term or section, semester and year). The most important aspect of the summative assessment is to find out at what level the students have achieved the application of the acquired knowledge. Summative assessment is a reliable indicator of the mastery level of content standards. (Scheme 10)

Scheme 10.

Various assessment methods and tools are used for data collection. The following can be attributed to them: 1. Assessment methods are the procedures used to collect information about students' learning activities; 2. Evaluation tools are tools used to implement that method; 3. Methods and tools differ

depending on the type of assessment. Recommendations on the methods and tools to be applied in diagnostic, formative and summative assessment have been included in scientific sources. Among them are the following recommendations, which we also appreciate: (Scheme 11.1; 11.2; 11.3):

Methods and tools used in diagnostic assessment (Scheme 11.1)

Methods	Means
Assignment	Studies
The interview	Teacher registration form
Cooperation with parents and other subject teachers	Conversation and teacher's questionnaire

Methods and tools used in formative assessment (Scheme 11.2)

Methods	Means
Oral and written presentation	Observation sheets, self-evaluation sheet
Research project	Criteria table
rubric (schema)	Criteria rating scale
Test	Test tasks
Self-assessment	Self-assessment sheets
Games	Observation sheets

Methods and tools used in summative assessment (Scheme 11.3)

Methods	Means
Project	Presentation
Oral inquiry	Question and answer
Test	Test tasks
Assignment	Assignment, study, laboratory work

We share the following generalizations: 1. Although test tasks are currently gaining popularity as an evaluation tool, the teacher teaching the subject should not be addicted to test tasks in diagnostic, formative and even summative evaluation; 2. Among the methods that develop students' oral and written speech skills, logical and analytical thinking, and the ability to think independently - project (evaluation tool - students' presentation and the criteria table drawn up by the teacher), oral survey (evaluation tool - registration sheet for oral speech skills), examination should make extensive use of written work (problem and example solution); 3. It is recommended to use test tasks not continuously, but whenever possible, and without hesitation in summative assessment. [9; 345-346]

We value rubrics highly in formative assessment. A rubric is a criterion-based assessment scale of a student's level of achievement. It answers two main questions: 1. What should I evaluate (skill criteria)? 2. What levels of achievement can be on this criterion? A rubric describes a skill or outcome on a continuum of increasing quality (low to high). A rubric can act as both a method and a means of assessment. A grading scale is a mechanism for assigning a grade (in points or words) to a level of achievement. [5; 295-297]

In addition to being one of the most useful forms of formative assessment, the rubric can also be used in diagnostic and summative assessment. (Scheme 12.1; 12.2)

Scheme 12.1

Scheme 12.2

Scheme 12.3

Rubrics have advantages. The mentioned aspects include: 1. Rubrics allow the assessment to be more fair, objective, reliable and consistent; 2. To develop rubrics, teachers define their own criteria for relevant conditions, which better describe learning objectives; 3. Rubrics reduce the time teachers spend on evaluating student work; 4. The rubrics provide teachers with useful information about the effectiveness of teaching; 5. Rubrics help assess telerogenic (differently abled) classrooms through a range of grade levels. [9; 345-346]

The process of preparing rubrics includes certain steps. In scientific sources, those steps are presented in the following order:

Step 1. Determine the name of the rubric by setting the training goal;

Step 2. Describe the aspects (criteria) (Express the description in the form of a scheme);

Step 3. Specifying the number of achievement levels (4-6 levels) and expression (indicators);

Step 4. Write a verbal description of all achievement level descriptors, identifying first the highest and lowest levels of the scale and then the scales in between. [15]

Regarding the comparison of holistic and analytical rubrics, the following generalizations can be presented, which are important for practical pedagogical activity:

1. Holistic assessment describes the overall picture of student achievement. Analytical evaluation determines the marks of the student in separate fields of activity, and provides more detailed information about the achievements of the students by consistently evaluating their activities.

2. Holistic assessment is fast, analytical assessment takes more time. [5; 299]

As mentioned, the holistic rubric provides an overall impression of the student's work and is often based on a 4-6 point scale that reflects performance levels.

Advantages: quick assessment, provides an overview of student achievement.

Weaknesses: does not provide detailed information, it may be difficult to give an overall assessment.

It is advisable to use holistic rubrics in the following cases:

1. When you want to get an instant picture of achievement;

2. If a single aspect is adequate to determine quality.

Analytical rubric, as mentioned, assigns separate grades for multifaceted aspects of the student's work (activity). A scale of 4-6 points is used to evaluate each aspect. The advantages of analytical rubrics include: they provide more detailed information, more consistent assessment is conducted for each student, grade and year. Weaknesses include: it takes a lot of time for evaluation (it takes time). It is advisable to use the analytical rubric in the following cases: a) when you want to see the relative advantage and weakness; b) when you want to get detailed information (feedback); c) when you want to evaluate a complex activity or

result; c) when students are asked to evaluate their own understanding or performance. [9; 348-349]

There are a number of recommendations for grading based on rubrics. These include: 1. Determine the training goal (knowledge, skills, attitudes, etc.); 2. Think about what you want students to know and be able to do; 3. Select the purpose of assessment (diagnostic, formative, summative); 4. Decide what type of rubric to use (holistic, analytical); 5. Determine the aspects (criteria) that are interesting for you and describe these aspects; 6. Determine how to express different levels of achievement; 7. Specify the number of achievement levels (or evaluation points); 8. State the level descriptors; 9. Write a verbal description of all achievement level descriptors.

It should be emphasized here that it is not enough to use only "quantitative evaluation" methods. Along with it, it is appropriate to use the following "qualitative assessment" methods: constructive notes in writing and checking works; "Portfolio" system; verbal (with words); mutual evaluation; self-assessment; removal of rating; evaluation through emotional attitude; benchmark table.

Scientific novelty and theoretical significance of the research work

1. The importance of the application of the "system-structure" approach method, formed as an important branch of the dialectic regarding the discovery of the essence of the subject curriculum and the determination of its application methods, was brought to the attention of researchers; 2. The solution of one of the cognitive issues that determines the solution of the problem of revealing the essence of the subject curriculum at the general education level and the optimal implementation of its application - "Interpretation of the characteristics of the elements of the "Evaluation of Student Achievements" block of the subject curricula applied in the general education schools of Azerbaijan based on the "system-structure" approach" was presented.

Practical significance of the research work

We hope that the research work will have a positive effect on the formation of the environment of revealing the essence of this or that subject curriculum applied at the general education level and eliminating some mistakes manifested in the activities of educators in the process of its application.

The result

1. The level of understanding of any real thing (objective existence) has a determining effect on the results of using it in adequate ways. 2. Making mistakes in the activities of educators in the application of any subject curriculum at the general education level has a negative effect on the efficiency level of the teaching process of this subject; 3. In the process of using the subject curriculum, the basis of the mistakes manifested in the activity of practical educators is based on a number of reasons, as well as a lack of honest enough understanding of its essence by these subjects; 4. "System-structure" approach is the most reliable dialectical method of understanding any existing thing, getting to its essence; 5. The dialectical method of "system-structure" approach regarding the discovery of

the essence of the subject curriculum and the determination of its application methods was not used in theoretical and technological directions; 6. One of the cognitive issues aimed at solving the problem that creates the basis for the manifestations of the error caused by the "gap" regarding the discovery of the essence of the subject curriculum and the determination of the ways of its application is the "system-structural" approach of the characteristics of the elements of the "Evaluation of Student Achievements" block of the subject curricula applied in general education schools of Azerbaijan. based on interpretation" and the research work presented in this direction benefits the teaching process of this or that subject.

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